

THE ESSENCE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN THE ECONOMY

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Abstract: In these articles, the scientific-theoretical foundations and essence of the digital economy are detailed. Also, developed countries' programs for digitalization of the economy were studied.

Key words: digitization, digital economy, digital technologies, economic development.

The emergence of the digital economy was based on the scientific views of a number of schools and trends in economic theory, namely marginalism, Keynesianism, institutionalism. In the process of formation of the digital economy, such sciences and technologies as economic and mathematical modeling, social psychology, information and telecommunication technologies were affected. That is, advanced technologies for data acquisition, transmission, processing and storage helped to emerge. As we noted above, the American programmer Nicholas Negoronte put the term "digital economy" into practice in 1995. Currently, all politicians, economists, journalists, businessmen around the world use this term. In 2016, the World Bank published its first report on the state of the digital economy in the world ("Digital Dividends").

Currently, there are different interpretations of the concept of "digital economy". Macalan, electronic (digital) economy - economic activity based on digital technologies; digital economy - a system of economic, social and cultural relations based on the use of digital and information communication technologies, as well as digital economy - information and communication technologies.

The concept of digital economy has been given a number of definitions. For example, V. Ivanov, Doctor of Economics, Corresponding Member of the Russian Academy of Sciences, defined that "Digital economy is a virtual environment that complements our reality." Tomsk State University professor R. Meshcheryakov believes that there are two approaches to the term "digital economy".

Raqamli texnologiyalar asosida iqtisodiyotning va elektron tovar va xizmatlar eksklyuziv domen tavsiflovchi raqamli iqtisodiyot: birinchi yondashuv “klassik” deb nomlanib, klassik misollar – teletibbiyot, masofaviy ta’lim, dori-darmonlarni sotish (filmlar, televizorlar, kitoblar va boshqalar). Ikkinchi yondashuv: “raqamli iqtisod” ilg‘or raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda iqtisodiy ishlab chiqarishdir. M.L. Kalujskiy “Raqamli iqtisodiyot – iqtisodiy internet faoliyati, shuningdek shakllari, usullari, vositalari va uni amalga oshirish aloqa muhitidir” – deb ta’riflagan

American futurologist K. Kelly gives the following more accurate definition: "Digital technologies and communications mean that communication is not just a branch of the economy, communication is the economy itself."

Academician Saidahrur Ghulomov from Uzbekistan says that digital economy is a science that studies the economic activity of a person, which envisages the widespread introduction of electronic and information and communication technologies in the processes of production, distribution and consumption of society's goods. describes. According to him, the term digital economy is used to represent two different concepts. First, the digital economy is considered a modern stage of development, characterized by the priority of creative work and information benefits. Secondly, the digital economy is a unique theory, the object of its study is the information society.

In the digital economy, information in digital form is the main element of production in all socio-economic fields, and the gradual transition to such an economic system will further increase the quality of life of citizens, create new jobs, and accelerate economic growth. enables and ensures national independence.

Implementation of the digital economy program in the Republic of Uzbekistan allows to achieve the following:

- complete elimination of legal obstacles that prevent the creation of new technologies by creating a new regulatory legal framework;
- creation and development of the infrastructure of the digital economy, including the development of networks, data processing centers, technical and software in accordance with the requirements of the time;
- ensuring comprehensive development and renewal of the educational system; mamlakatdagi turli-tuman kompaniyalar, firmalar, davlat korxonalarining hamda biznesning rivojlanishiga puxta asos yaratilishiga;
- the emergence of many organizations in the field of digital economy.

The table below shows the main strategic documents adopted by innovative developed countries regarding digitization.

Strategic planning documents in the field of digital economy in different countries

Table 1

China	"Made in China-2025", "Internet+", "National plan for stimulating technological developments in the field of artificial intelligence"
Germany	Germany "Digital Strategy 2025", "Industry 4.0"
US	US "Innovative Development Strategy", "US National Strategic Plan for the Development of Advanced Industrial Technologies"
France	France "Union for the Industry of the Future / New Industry France"
England	"UK Digital Strategy", "Information Economy Strategy"
Australia	Australia's National Strategy for the Digital Economy
Austria	"Industry 4.0 Austria"
Japan	"Smart Japan ICT Strategy"
Sweden "	"Smart Industry - Sweden's New Industrialization Strategy"
Netherlands	"Smart Industry"
Russia	"Digital economy of the Russian Federation" program
Uzbekistan	"Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" program

The digital economy development program should serve to achieve the following goals:

To create an ecosystem of the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- to create institutions and infrastructure of the country's digital economy system;
- to implement all necessary measures for the establishment of an information society covering all sectors of the republic;
- to increase the competitiveness of our republic on a global scale and in global markets.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 19, 2018 "On measures to further develop the field of information technologies and communications", July 3, 2018 "Measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan decisions about" can also be included in these measures. As a result of these measures, electronic document circulation was introduced, electronic payments are being developed, and the regulatory legal framework in the field of electronic commerce is being improved.

In general, today the role of the digital economy in the world is increasing. It is not for nothing that 2020 has been declared the "Year of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy Development" in our country. In our country, certain works are being carried out for the development of this sector. Undoubtedly, the digitalization of the economic sector creates opportunities such as reducing the costs associated with the production of goods and services, improving the quality of products, dramatically increasing the volume and competitiveness, and saving time. At the moment, digital technologies are widely used in Uzbekistan in the banking system, retail trade, transport, energy, education, healthcare and other fields. The digital economy significantly improves people's living standards, which is its main benefit. The digital economy is the main link of corruption and "black economy". Because numbers seal everything,

store it in memory, provide information quickly when needed. In such conditions, it is impossible to hide any information, make secret deals, not to provide full information about this or that activity, the computer will reveal everything. The abundance and systematicity of information does not allow for lies and fraudulent activities, because it is impossible to cheat the system. As a result, it will not be possible to launder "dirty money", steal funds, spend ineffectively and aimlessly, increase or hide it. This will increase the flow of legal funds into the economy, taxes will be paid on time and correctly, budget allocation will be open, funds directed to the social sphere will not be stolen, schools, hospitals, the money allocated for the roads will reach in full, etc.

The choice of the state to develop the digital economy opens up new directions in the field of information technologies and in general, in the field of circulation of electronic documents. The turn to "digital technologies" was caused by the development of the worldwide Internet network and quality communication.

Today, users are actively using Telegram bots to order food products. Also, various online stores and electronic payment systems are actively developing. Now the issue is the development of the implementation of medium and large economic transactions and financial transactions through digital technologies. In our country, special attention is paid to the formation of digital economy, in particular, to the introduction of advanced digital technologies into state and economic management. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and "On the approval of the strategy of Digital Uzbekistan - 2030 and measures for its effective implementation" In accordance with the decree, the most important tasks for the further development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan were defined as:

- activities in the field of crypto-asset circulation to diversify various forms of investment and business activities, including mining

(activities to provide a distribution platform that allows to receive rewards in the form of new units and commission fees in various cryptocurrencies, and to create new blocks), smart - contract (an electronic contract that provides for the fulfillment of rights and obligations through the automatic execution of digital transactions), consulting, issuance, exchange, storage, distribution, management, insurance, crowd-funding (collective financing), as well as "blockchain" technologies implementation and development;

- training qualified personnel with practical work skills using modern information and communication technologies in the field of development and use of "blockchain" technologies;
- comprehensive development of cooperation with international and foreign organizations in the field of activities on crypto-assets and "blockchain" technologies, attracting highly qualified foreign experts working in the field of development of "blockchain" technologies for joint implementation of projects in the digital economy;
- creation of the necessary legal framework for the introduction of "blockchain" technologies, taking into account the advanced experience of foreign countries; close cooperation of state bodies and business entities in the field of introducing innovative ideas, technologies and developments for the further development of the digital economy 'to provide;
- implementation of more than 280 information systems and software products for automation of management, production and logistics processes in enterprises in the real sector of the economy;
- relevant higher education institutions will be attached to improve the digital literacy and skills of governors, state bodies and employees of organizations, to train them in information technologies and information security, and 12,000 of their employees will be trained in the field of information technologies.

Digital technologies are reshaping many industries, including business,

transportation, and logistics. Digitization of the transport sector is also one of the consequences of the emergence of the digital economy. The contribution of the Internet and Social Network (IT) sector to the development of the digital economy is certainly high. According to the conclusions of the World Bank's study entitled "Digital Dividends", a 10% increase in Internet speed will lead to an increase in the country's Gross Social Product (GDP). In developed countries, this indicator is 1.21 percent, while in developing countries it is 1.38 percent. So, if the Internet speed doubles, it is possible to achieve a 13-14 percent increase in GDP. These indicators show how relevant and important the digital economy is in the development of the country's economy.

Also, starting from 2021, the implementation of "blockchain" technologies has been prioritized in the following areas:

- activities of state bodies, including cooperation with other state bodies and organizations, implementation of state purchases, provision of state services, verification of personal information;

- maintaining state registers, classifiers and other databases, including updating and using the information included in them;

- the system of corporate management of large commercial organizations in which the state's participation in the charter fund is a priority, including improvement of business processes, optimization of production, administrative and operational processes, as well as implementation of modern management and resource management;

- clearing operations, making payments, trade financing (letter of credit), as well as lending to projects.

Digital economy does not mean only Blockchain technology and its use in international financial markets or cryptocurrencies. Of course, Blockchain technology and cryptocurrencies are also part of the digital economy. But the digital economy (Digital Yeconomy) means the economy conducted with the help of digital communications and IT. In this case, it can also be considered as a

means of ending the underground economy. Because, firstly, all operations will be electronically registered, and secondly, they will be transparent. In addition, due to the use of new IT technologies in production, the cost of products and services will decrease¹.

The development of the digital economy is considered in three main segments:

- the sector of suppliers and buyers of real goods and services;
- sector of software and technology developers;
- infrastructure in the form of legal base, personnel training system, all types of data transmission and storage channels.

The directions of the digital economy are as follows:

- Big data;
- artificial intelligence;
- blockchain;
- quantum technologies;
- production technologies;
- industrial internet;
- robotics;
- wireless communication;
- virtual reality.

The National Project Management Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an authorized body in the field of introduction and development of the digital economy. In addition, the Ministries of Economy, Finance, Information Technology, Justice, and other state structures have specific responsibilities and tasks for the development of the digital economy.

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